

POLICIES FOR THE DISTRIBUTION OF GOODS IN THE FURNITURE INDUSTRY IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article discusses the development of distribution channels in the furniture market. On the example of a particularly enterprise, the problems of furniture production and its promotion in the market are raised.*

Keywords: *furniture market, product range, distribution channel.*

Introduction The head of state stressed that without increasing the competitiveness of the country's economy, without building a competitive economy and, ultimately, a competitive country, it is impossible to fulfill such a strategic task as bringing the country's economy to the level of developed democracies in Russia. medium term.

In the context of the globalization of the world economy, industrial enterprises of Uzbekistan must solve such important tasks as modernizing production, technical and technological renewal, increasing competitiveness, as well as investment attractiveness, increasing the volume of export-oriented products, and improving management. In accordance with the program approved by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 4, 2017 No. 1623 "On measures to expand and develop the production of new types of competitive products", measures are being taken to radically modernize the industry.

If we take a closer look at marketing activities in the furniture industry, we will see that the distribution of finished products is a key link in it. The internal reasons for this include the fact that contemporary furniture as a commodity responds to specific consumer needs, consumption patterns and the complexity of commercial services. The company must be able to convince the consumer that it is this furniture that he needs to sell his product, and show that his choice will be the most effective.

External reasons include fierce competition in the furniture market. At the same time, we can observe the influence of all competitive forces that M. Porter identified in his time.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process

Analysis and results. We clearly see the influence of competing companies in the location of furniture stores. The commercial goals and attitudes in this market are such that the customer is less likely to go to a single store located on the outskirts, as a result, all stores will be co-located, that is, most furniture stores are located in close proximity to each other. . In addition, many furniture manufacturers offer almost the same range of products in the process of adapting to the new fashion.

The impact of the introduction of new products is reflected in the rapid change in woodworking technologies, the use of new materials in furniture. Almost every year our country receives new equipment and efficient technologies for the production of furniture. This forces many products to enter the market. At the same time, the peculiarity of the furniture market is that even in a small store with simple equipment, an individual entrepreneur can enter this market and increase competition.

The behavior of buyers in the furniture market is also one of the competitive forces, their segmentation, demand differentiation, the rate of change in demand and price elasticity create a competitive environment.

Another aspect of the furniture industry is its dependence on raw materials. According to some reports, the country has the potential to grow a total of 31 million cubic meters of timber per year, but most of it cannot be used as a raw material for the furniture industry. This means that the industry is forced to use imported sapwood. This requires that suppliers be treated as a separate competitive force.

The influence of the above factors requires increased attention from furniture manufacturers to the development of the range and methods of selling goods.

Using the example of Gulobod Mebel LLC in Samarkand, we analyzed the distribution policy. Gulobod Mebel LLC in the first years of independence was formed from a small family business, and in 2003 it turned into an industrial enterprise. Today, its organizational position has grown to a group of modern large companies offering a variety of furniture to the market under the brand name MONDELUX. The following table presents the product range of Gulobod Mebel LLC in recent years.

Table 1
The composition of the assortment of Gulobod Mebel LLC in 2019-2022, %

No.	Furniture type	2019	2020	2021	2022
1	Furniture for kitchen	0.61	1.71	5.80	9.82
2	Cushioned furniture	24.23	23.97	26.09	25.15
3	Office furniture	32.32	30.82	31.88	29.45
4	Bedroom furniture	28.31	23.97	17.39	12.27
5	Wooden table and chairs	8.10	13.70	14.49	19.63
6	coffee tables	3.60	3.42	2.90	2.45
7	Mattress	2.80	2.41	1.45	1.23
	Jami	100	100	100	100

As can be seen from the data in the table, In 2019, the main part of the assortment was made up of three types of products - upholstered furniture (24.23%), office furniture (32.32%) and bedroom furniture (28.31%). The smallest place was occupied by kitchen furniture (0.61%). In 2020, we will see big changes in the range. Office furniture (29.45%) and upholstered furniture (25.15%) remained in the leading positions. The share of bed furniture fell sharply and amounted to 12.27%. The share of kitchen furniture production increased from 0.61% to 9.82%. Similarly, the production of wooden tables and chairs increased from 8.10% to 19.63%. The share of coffee tables and mattresses, which occupy a small place in the product range, decreased even more and in 2022 amounted to 2.45% and 1.23%, respectively..

The most important and integral component of marketing in the furniture market is the sale and distribution of the product. In this process, the most difficult task from an organizational point of view is the delivery of the product to the consumer.

A trading network can be defined as a structure formed by partners participating in a process of competitive exchange in order to provide goods or services to individual consumers or industrial users. These partners are manufacturers, resellers and end users. Any sales channel performs a certain set of functions necessary for conversion.

Due to the specifics of products manufactured by Gulobod Mebel LLC, sales are carried out through trading houses (table 2).

Table 2
Sales channels activity in Gulobod Mebel LLC in 2017-2020

No.	Company stores and centers	Sales volume by years				Annual change, %		
		2019	2020	2021	2022	2020	2021	2022
1	"Mondelux office" Furniture house.	1555	2081	2321	2598	133.8	111.5	111.9
2	Shopping center "Gulobod Mebel"	6044	6920	7264	7964	114.5	104.9	109.6
3	Trading House Mondelux Kitchen	-	102	1460	2936		1431.4	201.1
4	ENTER Engineering PTE.LTD	8906	9527	10454	11832	106.9	109.7	113.2
5	Atlas shopping complex, Tashkent	-	365	1066	1751		292.0	164.2
6	Trading House Mondelux	1336	1788	2073	2532	133.8	115.9	122.1
7	Trading House Mondelux Karshi	226	533	474	132	235.8	88.9	27.8
	Jami	18067	21316	25112	29745	117.9	117.8	118.4

As can be seen from this table, the most active trading houses are Nurobod trading house and Gulobod Mebel shopping center. They accounted for the bulk of sales in the period under review. In terms of growth rates, the Mondelux Kitchen Trading House and the Atlas shopping center in Tashkent are leading. The lowest place is occupied by the Karshi Trade Representation, and its activity is declining. At the same time, we can observe changes in the activities of trading houses and representative offices over the years. The marketing policy of the company does not provide for the use of intermediaries. The first reason is that production is tied to the consumer, and the second reason is that the company does not want to share transaction costs with others.

From this we can conclude that over the past three years there have been significant changes in the furniture market. The market position of Gulobod Mebel LLC is also changing. This, in turn, requires the development of the marketing activities of the enterprise.

The marketing program should also reflect the approach of Gulobod Mebel LLC to the promotion of goods based on its strategic goals in the market. One of the key aspects of this is to come to a common decision on how to organize communications with customers and how to measure their effectiveness.

One of the ways to develop e-commerce in Uzbekistan is to create trading platforms. This will give entrepreneurs the opportunity to advertise their products or services. We believe that the development of an order in social networks, the formation of e-commerce systems and the introduction of interactive advertising are very important areas.

The inclusion of these proposals in the marketing program of Gulobod Mebel LLC will ensure its viability and effectiveness.

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